

Importing S10 publications list from NIH Reporter to EndNote

1. Find and navigate to your S10 award on NIH Reporter (<https://reporter.nih.gov/>)
2. Click the Publications tab to see the list of publications associated with your grant (this means the authors cited it by award number)
3. Download (only option is .csv)
4. Double click to open csv file in Excel
5. Select Columns A & B and clear contents (Right-click, Clear Contents)
6. Add a blank line at the top of the sheet (Select the whole row, Right-click, Insert>Row)
7. In the first cell of the new line (A1), type *Generic
8. The second line will contain a list of fields. The fields of the csv file will not exactly match the accepted fields for EndNote:
 - a. Add a field in A2, by typing **Reference Type**
 - b. For each reference in the list, enter the Reference Type, i.e. Journal Article, Book, etc. (must match exactly the allowed Reference Types in EndNote)
 - c. In B2, type **Title** to add a new field (you will populate this in step 9)
 - d. Change the other fields to match the corresponding field names in EndNote (see Table below)
9. The titles of the articles are listed in Column O as html text. To strip off the URL formatting:
 - a. Select B3 and copy and paste the formula below, carriage return to apply:
$$=MID(O3,(FIND(">",O3,1))+1,(FIND("</a",O3,1)-1)-(FIND(">",O3,1)))$$
 - b. Autofill the formula for the rest Column B by selecting the cell dragging the green handle down the column
 - c. Select all entries in Column B, copy and paste special in place so the entries in the column are value only and not formulas (Copy>Paste Special>Values)
 - d. Delete the Column O (with the URL formatted article titles)
10. Delete any columns you don't want to import e.g. citations, impact factors, etc.
11. Save the Excel file as Tab-delimited text (ignore all warnings)
12. Open the text file in MS Word
13. Show hidden characters by clicking the ¶ at the top right of the ribbon

14. Delete the extra tabs (looks like arrows) between the word Generic and the paragraph marker at the end of the first line
15. Find and replace all “ with nothing
16. Save the file as Unicode UTF-8 (ignore all warnings)
17. Go to EndNote and choose File>Import and select the file
18. Use References>Find Reference Updates... to fill in missing fields not included in the original export from NIH Reporter.

Field Name Conversions (Taken from EndNote21>Settings>Journal Article>Modify Reference Types)

NIH Reporter	EndNote
Authors	Author
Title (Link to full-text in PubMed Central)	Title
Journal Title ABBR	Secondary Title
Journal Volume	Volume
Journal Issue	Number
Page Number	Pages
PMC ID	Custom 2 (user defined in EndNote)
ISSN	ISBN/ISSN